

Specialisation and collaboration in the European Network of DIHs:

Leading the way to a European Innovation Support Infrastructure

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0 Abstract:

Digital Innovation Hubs (DIH) have emerged as a European approach for more effective diffusion of digital technologies. DIHs develop skills and offer supporting services for digital transformation, in particular in SMEs and more recently also in public administration. This approach is based on state-of-the-art innovation ecosystem policy and best practices of innovation support infrastructures.

To support sustainable collaboration in the EU ecosystem an alignment of-hubs in a European framework of specialisation and collaboration is needed. In this paper we suggest that the network of DIHs and future European DIHs can be a mechanism for the wider European Innovation Support Infrastructure needed for industrial transformation, by means of 'collaborative specialisation'.

The DIH network can be a trailblazer for a truly European Innovation Support Infrastructure which will provide links to capacities, facilities and expertise for the twin digital and green transitions as well as supporting the shift to a more resilient EU. However, finding the right focus and complementarities requires a leadership approach on collaborative specialisation. The establishment of 'corridors' between EDIHs can be the tipping-point for more structural collaboration between European industrial ecosystems.

1. Introduction

Digital Innovation Hubs – and similar entities such as R&I test beds, field labs, pilot lines etc. – have become an important instrument in the innovation systems in many European countries. The movement started first in the manufacturing sector and subsequently migrated to a variety of other sectors from agriculture and chemicals to health. Across Europe we find now over 400 DIHs¹. This rapid growth in number reflects the widely acknowledged need for such hubs to support the diffusion and adoption of cutting edge innovation and technology. But, the DIH concept is dynamic and comes in many variations. As a result, after five years of developing the concept of DIHs, we now find in Europe a highly dynamic and still somewhat unstructured landscape with DIHs that serve sectoral, local and regional needs, (supra) regional coordinating hubs, national platforms and cross-border initiatives. DIHs cannot be everything to all people and cannot be expert in all fields. As they gain importance within a place-based (regional) innovation policy they will add value through specialisation and collaboration. The upcoming addition of the 'European' DIHs (EDIHs) provides another rationale for looking again at patterns of specialisation and collaboration within and across borders.

Digital Innovation Hubs were proposed as one of the five pillars in the Digitising European Industry initiative, co-developed between the European Commission (DG Connect) and the Member States in 2015. Building on previous efforts to support the technological development and innovation of companies, the DIHs combine technological expertise with business and ecosystem services to support innovative companies in their digital transformation. DIHs support industry in their digital transition by aiming to provide **one-stop shops** in every region and a strong network to ensure that every company can have **access** to these opportunities. Further discussion has emphasised the **eco-system**, and the place-based approach for these hubs, and their **connection with smart specialisation strategies** (S3). The conceptual distinction between 'competence centres', the 'DIH', the 'regional

¹ <https://s3platform.jrc.ec.europa.eu/digital-innovation-hubs-catalogue>

network of DIHs' and the 'trans-European network' of services has brought further clarification² in line with the ecosystem and place-based approach to innovation. Smart specialisation strategies (S3) and the DIH network are arguably the key inputs to **EU-wide regional innovation policy frameworks**.

With the upcoming Digital Europe Programme (DIGITAL) and the new European Digital Innovation Hubs (EDIH), the DIH strategy aims to support the objective of uptake and deployment of digital technologies in Europe. Member States have **nominated** candidates for the selection of 'European Digital Innovation Hubs' for this Programme³, thus engaging both the regional and national policy levels.

With the start of the new programming period dominated by the Green Deal and the post-Corona recovery plan there is a need to **anchor** the DIHs in the green and digital transformation agenda and **consolidate** the strategic approach of the DIH network that has emerged in the past few years in this context.

But in order to share the same understanding of the challenge, the DIHs and EDIHs still need to explore how to respond to basic questions on how to handle different **types of specialisation** at the level of the European innovation ecosystem: such as the geographical coverage, the distribution of services, the focus on specific domains, such as technology, sectors, applications or missions, etc.

Therefore, the key issue is how to combine specialisation and collaboration, and how to make this kind of cooperation the cornerstone of innovation support infrastructures for the twin green and digital transitions. This requires both a strong future vision and a practical methodology on how to best forge structural collaborations between DIHs.

2. Purpose of the document

This document is an input for a new learning cycle on the content and implementation of specialisation and collaboration processes in the context of DIHs and the imminent launch of the European Digital Innovation Hubs (EDIHs). The Digital Europe Programme provides a policy space for the acceleration of specialisation and collaboration for the EU-wide implementation of digital transformation across the whole population of DIHs. The 'Thought Leadership'⁴ process aims at structuring this learning process in three different building blocks which explore how DIHs (in particular EDIHs) can practically collaborate, and offer suggestions for future policy development.

- 1) A first building block analyses **the challenges of DIH**: to be a one-stop shop for SMEs in their regions vs. the need to specialise in certain technologies, domains or sectors; to diffuse but also advance digital technologies; to focus on 'digital' and integrate this in all domains; to specialise and to collaborate.
- 2) In order to structure best practices and guidance, we propose in the second building block the '**collaborative specialisation**' approach (including practices for discovering smart complementarities with mapping and matching) in a leadership vision for DIH. This could contribute to exploring and developing 'corridors', structural cooperation between DIHs.

² DIHNET (2020), "Defining Digital Innovation Hubs as part of the European DIH network (DRAFT)"r

³ European Digital Innovation Hubs in Digital Europe Programme Draft working document 05-05-2020

⁴ 'Thought Leadership' is one of the tasks of the DIHNET, where transversal topics are raised to initiate discussion and support the DIHNET and general DIH community.. It was proposed in response to comments during the first DIHNET Project Review and included in the project amendment in 2020.

- 3) A third building block analyses the future of the DIH in the evolving **policy framework for the transition to a digital, green and resilient economy**. The leadership vision aims at anchoring the DIH in a shared narrative on the need for a European Innovation Infrastructure to support the digital transformation as a backbone of the new growth model.

3. Vision⁵

Collaboration and specialisation have been discussed in the past, but given the upcoming Digital Europe Programme and leading European strategies like the Green Deal it is important to further develop the ideas of how collaboration and specialisation can be organised both at the operational (practical) level of the (E)DIHs and at the policy level.

To this end, we propose the following policy options and recommendations to support the development of a collaborative European innovation ecosystem and a sharing of access to innovation infrastructures.

1. Effective specialisation and collaboration at European level.

A key challenge for the operationalisation of the DIHs and EDIHs is to integrate the seemingly differing requirements of being a regional **one-stop-shop** addressing the needs of local SMEs, and of offering added value by their **specialisation** to SMEs and other actors across borders. This can only be achieved by **place-based innovation strategies** embedded in the regional innovation ecosystems **that are interconnected at European level**. (E)DIH therefore should be linked to the regional policies such as the Smart Specialisation Strategies as a common European policy framework for cooperation for transformation. The coming selection of European DIHs (EDIH) provides a **mandate** for these selected consortia to co-develop a European network of innovation support and connect infrastructures and related services to enhance the digital transformation within regions and across borders. Specialisation and cooperation in the European network of EDIHs can be organised around **mapping** the unique competences in each region and **discovering⁶** the complementarities in the European network for supporting business opportunities in new value chains for a green, digital and resilient economy. Based on the emerging structural collaborations of strategic nature, a multiplication of such 'corridors' could be used to enhance the growth of effective cooperation networks.

2. A trailblazer of the European innovation infrastructure.

European cooperation for systemic transformation requires a shared narrative incorporating the role of different European programmes and policy levels. This policy narrative will be a crucial element to grow long-term expectations for the role of support entities like DIHs and **to align investments in complementary infrastructures**. The upcoming European Digital Innovation Hub programme is a window of opportunity for European innovation policy **to accelerate the pace towards a collaborative European Innovation System Infrastructure**. This innovation infrastructure is the backbone for co-developing new value propositions, especially in strategic areas for European growth, through the diffusion of innovation, the deployment of key

⁵ Ideas contributed by Friends of Smart Specialisation

⁶ The 'Entrepreneurial Discovery Process' is a governance mechanism to ensure that stakeholders that want to commit their resources for future growth opportunities of the region, are fully involved in the strategic prioritisation and implementation.
https://www.researchgate.net/publication/339068135_Smart_Specialisation_at_work_The_entrepreneurial_discovery_as_a_continuous_process

technologies, access to demonstration activities, pilot actions and the testing of solutions to challenges. This is a chance to position EDIH, with their close connection to Test & Experimentation Facilities in the core of the development of the European industrial ecosystems⁷. There is also an opportunity to connect the future EDIHs with the present discussion on the new role of the European Research Area in developing a strategy for European technology infrastructures and the introduction of 'ERA Hubs'.⁸

4. Specialisation and collaboration from the DIH perspective

4.1 Specialisation in the DIHs

How can DIHs and upcoming selected EDIHs integrate the seemingly opposite requirements of being a regional **one-stop-shop** addressing the needs of local SMEs, and of offering added value by services in areas of **specialisation** (also to SMEs 'abroad')? The profile of 'first line' adviser and general support is different from 'specialised' expert for specific domains. The diffusion of the 'best available technology' (specialisations) across regions will ensure high quality services, close to the frontier. By collaborating at the EU level, DIHs can further develop their focus area while at the same time providing access to expertise and capacities of other DIHs and learn from each other.

To discuss these questions of specialisation and collaboration, it is necessary to distinguish different types of 'specialisation' seen within the DIHs and how this typology relates to 'smart specialisation'. While different types of specialisation may be distinguished for different purposes, in the experience of DIH we consider generally **four types of specialisation**⁹ (could also be more or combined):

- **Technology specialisation:** DIHs often focus on a specific technology such as robotics, AI, HPC and offer services connected to these technologies to different sectors¹⁰. DIHs, in addition, are specialised in services for technology development at higher TRL levels, testing and prototyping and/ or on business development. With the EDIHs and DEP, the focus is on the uptake of technologies in general i.e. closer to technology deployment.
- **Sector specialisation:** many DIHs focus specifically on economic sector(s) in accordance with the strengths of the region. We find DIH addressing digitization in manufacturing, in healthcare and in agriculture for instance. But sector borders become blurred and are replaced by other categories.¹¹

We also see hubs **combining sector and technology specialisations**: e.g. hubs focusing on robotics for healthcare. The DEP puts a focus on AI, HPC, cybersecurity but also includes other technologies and recognizes the importance of sector focus. This focus should be

⁷ see 'A New Industrial Strategy for Europe' https://ec.europa.eu/info/strategy/priorities-2019-2024/europe-fit-digital-age/european-industrial-strategy_en

⁸ https://ec.europa.eu/info/news/era-communication-sets-pace-efficient-uptake-research-and-innovation-results-2020-sep-30_en

⁹ This categorisation is not exhaustive. It is all about identifying 'activity domains'. We single out 'technology specialisation' and '(economic) sector specialisation' as different sub-types in this 'domain specialisation'. They have established classifications (such as IPC patent codes and NACE codes). 'Application areas' can be used as demand-side specialisation areas with although less clear classification. Preferred 'thematics' (often policy priorities) is also a way to distinguish domain specialisations.

¹⁰ See <https://consultation.onlines3.eu/2-6-specialisation-indexes>. 'Specialisation' of an entity (company, region, country, ...) compares the share of a technology across all technologies (in terms of expenditures or patents etc) in this entity with the share of this technology across all entities.

This relative specialisation reveals the comparative advantage of the entity.

¹¹ In the context of political priority setting thematic 'domains' come to the foreground, often linked to challenges (such as the policy priorities in cohesion policy). But the specification of domains is not referring to a consistent methodology for delimitation of areas (like Nace codes, patent codes, Nuts codes, ...).

based on competitive strengths and addressing future needs of the local ecosystem and their integration in European value chains.¹²

- **Service specialisation:** DIHs provide four types of services: ecosystem, business, technology, skills development. These are also reflected in the four types of services expected by the new EDIHs. But DIHs will only be able to provide direct, first line support to SMEs in a limited number of technologies or sectors. For other questions that they cannot provide direct solutions, they may either provide information to SMEs or broker support from other institutions (DIHs, universities, RTOs) inside or outside the region.
- **Regional specialisation:** Many regions have adopted smart specialisation strategies that aim to integrate local supply side (resource availability / sector strengths) and demand side (specific priorities for societal needs such as ageing or climate change) issues. A DIH will be geographically focused and has a mix of services that is also specific for the area or domain it is working on. But the 'domain specialisation' will possibly be the most important characteristic for aligning efforts with other DIHs to support technology and business development in their ecosystems and value chains. Projects addressing challenges of different nature in the targeted domain will combine different supply and demand-side specialisations in EU-wide value chains. Specialisation is always connected to collaboration with matching specialisations within a domain. It is therefore important that DIHs build on and further strengthen the smart specialisation strategies of regions and their interregional collaboration.

4.2. Connecting Smart Specialisation Strategies and DIHs

'Smart specialisation' is one of the main specialisation and collaboration mechanism currently in place in Europe. Compared with the types discussed above, 'Smart specialisation' is not just a 'functional' distinction in the way ecosystems are structured. It is a policy approach for prioritising public innovation investments in activities that are identified (with the Entrepreneurial Discovery Process¹³) to be strategic for future economic (sustainable) growth within a defined territory. Business innovation support by the public (including cluster platforms and technological support infrastructures) is earmarked in smart specialisation strategies for specific domains that are of strategic importance for the region's economic development and international competitiveness. The identification of these priority domains and activities is a 'political' (stakeholder-based) preference for future focused investments in the region.

Many DIHs are connected to the Smart Specialisation strategies in their countries and a report from JRC also points that many DIHs are also participating in the consultation processes or even the drafting of the S3.¹⁴ This link becomes ever more important in the new programming period. It is already foreseen that Member States can use structural funds (ERDF) for co-financing the set-up of EDIHs.¹⁵

¹² In modern industrial policies the sector approach is absorbed in a wider 'industrial ecosystem' approach that is value chain based and therefore cross-sectoral.

¹³ See <https://s3platform.jrc.ec.europa.eu/entrepreneurial-discovery-edp>;
<http://www.know-hub.eu/knowledge-base/videos/entrepreneurial-discovery-process.html>

¹⁴ See for example Gabriel Rissola, Jens Sörvik (2018), Digital Innovation Hubs in Smart Specialisation Strategies: Early lessons from European regions, JRC Technical Report

¹⁵ "A prerequisite for investments of ERDF in Digital Innovation Hubs for services under categories "Test before invest (in digital technologies)" and "(Digital) skills and training" is that these are fully supporting the regional or national smart specialisation strategy" 'European Digital Innovation Hubs in Digital Europe Programme Draft working document 22-10-2020', p14, <https://ec.europa.eu/digital-single-market/en/european-digital-innovation-hubs-digital-europe-programme-0>

Given that ERDF funds are connected to S3 strategies, the cross-regional collaboration of DIHs becomes intertwined with **interregional partnering for implementation of smart specialisation strategies**. The operationalisation of services across borders will always have to be fitted in other regional, national and European programmes.¹⁶

4.3. Collaborative specialisation in the European DIH Network with 'mapping and matching'

The digital transformation requires a quantitative and qualitative upgrade in technology diffusion efforts. How can the DIH network live-up to this task? On the basis of experiences in S3 partnerships with the model 'learn-connect-match-commercialise'¹⁷, the 'mapping' and 'matching' have proven to be crucial steps to set-up connections between competence centres in joint projects for the testing and demonstration of new solutions. Interregional collaboration for smart specialisation can develop into 'collaborative specialisation' when the competitive specialisations in regions become aligned.¹⁸

This capacity to align can develop organically from the core functions of (E)DIHs. The DIHs need to make a continuous mapping at regional level of relevant infrastructures and services and of competences of their relevant partners to offer the best support to digital transformation journeys. The journey starts with a **common challenge or a mission** that urges for cooperation, because the different organisations cannot do it alone and are open to find partners with complementary specialisations. This continuous monitoring therefore also becomes the basis of collaboration with other DIHs through **exchanging and combining mappings** of their best assets in specific value domains of common interest.

The future 'Digital Transformation Accelerator'¹⁹ – the details of which are still under discussion at the time of writing – might catalyse such discovery process of joint opportunities among EDIHs with appropriate **technical support for mapping and matching**. Starting from a challenge, the mapping exercise starts a roadmap for partnering in specific value creating actions (i.e. demonstrating and testing digital innovations with combined efforts). The mapping is therefore a method for matching the partners that are complementary for high-class services, and also to identify overlaps that might need a more focused differentiation.. Such a process of mapping and matching can be put in motion already at an early stage, starting from the experience of the thematic smart specialisation platforms²⁰ and the use of the Catalogue as a matching tool.

Empirical knowledge on the best practices for collaborative integrated approaches in deployment of technology for targeted use also needs to be studied. This experience is now scattered across many collaborative programmes. The present support actions (like I4MS, etc.) and umbrella organisations

¹⁶ The challenge is to avoid a fragmentation of policy and administrative frameworks that burdens the build-up of a long-term strategy for EDIH (need to go shopping around!). Besides ERDF also EAFRD can be used for co-financing the 50% DEP-funding. Horizon Europe support companies that work with DIH; DIH can be intermediaries to additional Invest EU financing. The most important resource might become the Recovery and Resilience Facility that labels 20% of funding for digital (including DIH). But this diversity also hinders a common DIH mission.

¹⁷ <https://www.s3vanguardinitiative.eu/pilotinitiatives>

¹⁸ www.interregeurope.eu/policylearning/news/8696/interregional-collaboration-for-smart-specialisation-methodological-tools/?no_cache=1&chash=e4c69f7fdef08d0b9dc0b7fc91ea6c29

¹⁹ "The organisation of this collaboration will be supported through a support facility called the "Digital Transformation Accelerator". This name signifies the importance of this action: it should animate all networking and collaboration activities and through that accelerate the digital transformation everywhere in Europe", in 'European Digital Innovation Hubs in Digital Europe Programme Draft working document 22-10-2020'. See <https://ec.europa.eu/digital-single-market/en/european-digital-innovation-hubs-digital-europe-programme-0>, p x

²⁰ Methodological Manual, S3 Platform, <https://s3platform.jrc.ec.europa.eu/-/methodological-manual-developing-thematic-interregional-partnerships-for-smart-specialisation?inheritRedirect=true>

for support infrastructures (like EBN, IASP, the European Cluster Collaboration Platform) and platforms for cooperation (like the S3 thematic platforms) can be partner in this empirical finding of such strategic mutual support capacity. The European Enterprise Network (EEN) is already designated to be a key partner with regard to EDIHs.²¹ But a way forward to accelerate learning about collaborative specialisation, already in the 2021 preparatory period, is to task the future EDIHs to further describe their focus in a joint mapping of specialised infrastructures across regions in support of missions²² or strategic value chains in the 14 industrial ecosystems identified for European industrial policy.²³

4.4 Structural Cooperation in the EDIH network: emergence of corridors

The network of EDIHs can provide the steppingstones to new, more sustained forms of pan-European collaboration in the benefit of industrial transformation. At present the dominant form of European collaboration between 'hubs' of all kind that offer R&I services to industry is project-based and therefore mostly of an ad-hoc nature. Project funding is the basic funding model for European collaboration. This is a competitive and flexible form but also requires high coordination costs which limit the learning and trust-building over the longer term. While projects can often be one-off collaboration opportunities, more structured alliances (both formal and informal) partner networks play an important background role (and will continue to do so).

But to make transformation possible on the level of European ecosystems and value chains, these background collaborations have to come to the foreground. A sustained collaboration in the provision of innovation services between the network nodes needs strong channels. Such channels are 'corridors' for structural cooperation in a still fragmented and opaque European landscape of services available in regional innovation infrastructures and ecosystems.

To promote and forge the establishment of more 'corridors' for more structural collaboration between digital innovation hubs two preconditions seem to be needed: a (political) mandate and an orchestrating capacity. The one without the other is doomed to fail.²⁴

All of the present structural collaborations are based on some kind of strategic alliance, such as those illustrated below, and some of which are based on current experience with existing DIHs. Often, they are facilitated by a political mandate:

- An early example of cooperative framework is ELAt: the Aachen, Leuven, Eindhoven Triangle, that is an institutional approach for cross-border cooperation based on these cities. Regional authorities are the cement for the longer-term cooperation for technology transfer between knowledge institutes.

²¹ Annex - Seamless Collaboration Between Enterprise Europe Network And European Digital Innovation Hubs, in 'European Digital Innovation Hubs in Digital Europe Programme Draft working document 22-10-2020'. See <https://ec.europa.eu/digital-single-market/en/european-digital-innovation-hubs-digital-europe-programme-0>, P 40

²² Missions are defined in Horizon Europe (https://ec.europa.eu/info/horizon-europe/missions-horizon-europe_en); strategic value chains are identified in European Industrial Ecosystems (https://ec.europa.eu/info/strategy/priorities-2019-2024/europe-fit-digital-age/european-industrial-strategy_en)

²³ https://ec.europa.eu/info/strategy/priorities-2019-2024/europe-fit-digital-age/european-industrial-strategy_en#transforming-our-industry

²⁴ Experience of smart specialisation strategies indicates that strong political leadership and good governance and capacity are required for robust and successful strategies.

- The Vanguard Initiative²⁵ is an alliance of more than thirty regions that was created as a political initiative to increase the role of ambitious regions in European industrial policy (Milan Declaration of 2014).²⁶ This gave rise to a number of 'pilots' that evolved to S3 partnerships that structure a longer-term interregional cooperation between a number of regional actors (clusters, technology centres, universities) in common priority areas for industrial transformation. These stable networks are a source of joint projects.
- Basque Country and Lombardy have recently concluded a more dedicated agreement to facilitate cooperation for innovation, based on trust building and mutual understanding of complementarities through multiple collaborations. Bilateral arrangements between regions and countries exist already for a long-time and have initiated or reinforced 'corridors' but were limited to science cooperation.
- Arrangements to use innovation infrastructure are already structured in cross-border Interreg projects (such as between Hungary and Austria) or/and in Macro-Regions programmes. Sometimes this allows to cross-border research infrastructure.²⁷ Cohesion policy is a major lever for 'corridors', using infrastructures and services as channels, but it has not sufficient instruments for sustained interregional cooperation.²⁸ The 'political will' of the regions for an outward looking innovation policy is however the basic condition.
- Sometimes the innovation actors themselves have taken the initiative to establish strategic cooperation, such as 'Silicon Europe', the alliance between the cluster organisations of the leading micro-electronic regions, that are longstanding partners in European projects. The European Cluster Collaboration Platform promotes European cluster cooperation.²⁹ European associations of innovation actors such as EARTO are also providing frameworks for structural cooperation between RTOs. But these bottom-up 'interest groups' need a political mandate to play a role in the architecture of structural collaboration at trans-European level.

A programme framework for promoting more project based cooperation (such as most digital innovation hub programmes up to now) is a first step. But more is needed to address the challenges of structural transformations. Collaboration can exist at different levels of engagement and ambition. The establishment of more structured and aligned corridors requires an orchestrating capacity and strategic purpose and commitment that go beyond participation in one call or even an entire programming period. The added value of structural cooperation is not only to drastically increase policy learning and technology transfer but it is a next step to develop purposeful structural synergies and targeted participation in European value chains, which is the new challenge for any region that wants to position itself (and its actors) in the twin transition. This is about building critical mass and strategic purpose and about spending R&I budgets wisely by avoiding duplication. Strategy needs to be supported by a capacity to act, to orchestrate the conditions for successful collaboration between hubs and ecosystems.

²⁵ <https://www.s3vanguardinitiative.eu/>

²⁶ https://www.s3vanguardinitiative.eu/sites/default/files/contact/image/final_declaration_of_milan_final_27_10.pdf

²⁷ The INL International Iberian Nanotechnology Laboratory, located in Braga (North of Portugal) was founded by the governments of Portugal and Spain under an international legal framework to perform interdisciplinary research, deploy and articulate nanotechnology for the benefit of society.

²⁸ A first breakthrough is the I3 'Interregional Innovation Investments', see <https://www.interregeurope.eu/future/InterregionalInvestment>

²⁹ Recently the cluster cooperation is also structured according to the 14 Industrial eco-systems, <https://clustercollaboration.eu/in-focus/industrial-ecosystems>

The orchestrating capacity can be developed in multiple forms. Some of these are:

- Bottom-up initiatives of (E)DIHs (with their lead-institutes, lead-clusters) themselves to foster solid partnerships (see above)³⁰. Although this happens already, it needs to multiply and deepen by supportive network services such the Catalogue and by exploiting mapping and matching, in cooperation with the EEN and other service providers.
- Regional authorities have also created corridors with dedicated partnerships, and can structure complementarities further by using their smart specialisation strategies in an outward looking way. They can commit to S3 partnerships, that involve their (E)DIHs (and their own support instruments), with the help of facilitators such as the Vanguard Initiative, the S3 Platform and other levers such as the EIT.
- The European initiative for a Digital Transformation Accelerator – still to be designed and a call for proposals to be launched- can possibly become a more top-down orchestrating instrument for matchmaking in the EDIH network, but this can only be successful if it accepts multi-level governance to align support instruments along the whole innovation trajectory and the value chain.
- Strategic cooperation on research and technological development is already shaped by existing structures such as joint technology initiatives (JTIs) and Joint Programming Initiatives (JPIs) and public private partnerships (PPPs). But we are now witnessing the development of a new layer for technology infrastructures in the European Research and Innovation Area (ERA), with its four aims of prioritising investments and reforms in R&I to support the digital and green transition and Europe's recovery; improving access to excellent R&I for researchers across the EU; translating results into the economy to ensure market uptake of research output and Europe's competitive leadership in technology and making progress on the free circulation of knowledge, researchers and technology through stronger cooperation with EU countries.³¹

5. Specialisation and collaboration from a policy perspective

5.1 Role of the DIH network in the development of a European Innovation System

The new EDIH pillar of the DEP is a window of opportunity for innovation policy in Europe to accelerate the pace towards a more integrated European Innovation System Infrastructure, with as a core the European DIH-network and its common European mission. This innovation infrastructure should aim at developing new value propositions, in particular, in strategic areas for European growth, with the deployment of technologies, demonstration and testing of solutions to challenges.

A systematic interconnection of such facilities and services for deployment is lacking in the EU. The establishment of this European innovation infrastructure is now one of the crucial conditions to close the innovation gap thanks to revamped European innovation policies that fully engage all resources to the common challenges outlined in the Green Deal and digital transformation and needed for the recovery and resilience of our economies after the pandemic.

³⁰ At present several Community Support Actions and Innovation Actions build network capacity to connect DIHs, beyond their project life-time. E.g. the 'Photon Hub' seeks to develop a partnership of (7) regions that will provide an annual structural funding after the end of the project in 2024 for. I4MS and Smart Everything Everywhere (SEA) have ambitions to become a community platform, with services for DIHs.

³¹ [European research area \(ERA\) | European Commission \(europa.eu\)](#)

The European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures (ESFRI) is already providing a roadmap coordinating cooperation and investment for European research infrastructures. This important strategic think-tank, received a mandate in the new ERA action plan to broaden its scope to all technology infrastructures.³² But the (E)DIH network can be the start of a Europe-wide approach to deployment, go-to-market and solutions for mission-oriented research and strategic innovation. That is because the (E)DIH is a connector of the different functions that are required for supporting the digital transformation in companies and value chains. In addition, the EDIH is also a connector of the digital eco-system with policy makers at regional, national and European level. This gives them a unique position, that only can be implemented with their organisation as a well-functioning network.

5.2. The role of the EDIH in particular

This potential of a European policy framework for DIH is illustrated by the fact that more than 400 organisations are listed in the 'Catalogue of Digital Innovation Hubs'.³³ The EDIH programme wants to achieve Europe-wide coverage of support services to SMEs, but also a European added value expressed in selection criteria for networking and specialisation for European DIHs.

The coming selection of European DIHs is providing, therefore, a **mandate** to the selected consortia to co-develop a European network of technology infrastructures and related services to support the digital transformation in the regions and across borders.

EDIHs may have a role in the diffusion of state-of-the-art digital technology and innovation. Each EDIH can provide the necessary scale in each region for an integrated deployment approach by means of strong consortia of competence centres, professional innovation service providers and strong local networks for additional services and financial leverage. But the 'European added value' is in their interregional specialisation and cooperation.

A clear message should be articulated that EDIHs receive funding not only for their function to support the regional ecosystem but also to establish and sustain EU collaboration. To this end the business model for the sustained functioning of these hubs and of their network must be a central focus in this formation period. EU funding should not be just another source of project funding for these 'hubs' (as ad-hoc consortia) but contribute to a more strategic/structural approach for sustaining a European innovation infrastructure in the medium and long-term? Therefore, the European DIH network has to gain recognition as a common resource from different policy fields that share the same European strategic goals. Different instruments can contribute to a stable funding mix. The European DIH network is a trailblazer, provided it can deliver an efficient and effective mechanism to align resources for collaboration and specialisation on common challenges.

5.3. DI Hubs and ERA Hubs: towards a new narrative for shared innovation infrastructure at EU level

The success of the DIH network is a **shared ambition and responsibility** for policy leaders (supporting the network with instruments at regional, national and European level) and for entrepreneurial (E)DIHs (driving the network potential to European scale). There is a need to have an integrative policy framework for the different funding sources and tools of different policy domains and levels

³² <https://www.esfri.eu/esfri-roadmap-2021>

³³ <https://s3platform.irc.ec.europa.eu/digital-innovation-hubs-tool>

In order for the EDIH initiative to play its role as trailblazer of the European innovation infrastructure and European cooperation for systemic transformation there is a need for a shared narrative about European innovation cooperation, across policies and programmes at European level. This will be a crucial element for long-term expectations that can nurture new business models for the DIHs. The previous analysis has tried to clarify the role of (E)DIH as one-stop shops for a diffusion policy, and their internationalisation in perspective of 'collaborative specialisation' to cover complementary support actions to companies in the development of specific European value chains. The programme for the European Network of EDIHs has the potential to be a key enabler of that potential, in particular in developing 'corridors' for structural collaboration. This collaborative specialisation needs an accommodating policy framework that should be provided by a combined top-down and bottom-up approach towards the European role of innovation infrastructures. Green Deal and European Industrial Policy are giving high-level direction. Smart specialisation strategies are a bottom-up policy approach towards aligning specialisations across borders and combining assets to avoid fragmentation. The EDIHs establish a growing texture of corridors to channel collaborative specialisation.

The streamlining of the different European policy initiatives on 'hubs' is a success condition for the necessary 'top-down' policy framework that has a role in providing direction. A core feature in this long-term vision is to combine the technology diffusion approach (AI, HPC, etc) with a solution based approach, integrating different technologies for common missions and solutions for industry and society. This requires integration of policies for promoting core digital technologies with policies for other (domain specific) technologies and their infrastructures. The latter will become more and more digitised in their operation. Policy silos are a system failure.³⁴ The integrated European technology infrastructure is a network of flexible combination and integration of the necessary services for a tailor-made support to new value creation in promising areas for regional, national and European sustainable growth.

During the Research & Innovation Days in September 2020, Commissioner Gabriel announced the launch of '**ERA Hubs**', as "regional organisations **similar to the EU's Digital Innovation Hubs**".³⁵ This is a welcome evolution, provided it avoids duplication. In the EC Communication of 30 September 2020 on 'A new ERA for Research and Innovation' this ambition is formulated as:

"Based on a mapping of existing entities, and the analysis of potential gaps, an *ERA Hubs* initiative could be developed, building on existing capacities, such as the Digital Innovation Hubs and clusters, and linking to the Enterprise Europe Network and StartUpEurope, to provide an interconnected knowledge space. This will facilitate collaboration and exchange of best practices, with the incentive to maximise the value of knowledge production, circulation and use".³⁶

³⁴ First signs of such integration of narratives is seen in the connection made between EDIHs and the 14 industrial ecosystems: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=HGAex6zLWwY&feature=youtu.be>

³⁵ See <https://sciencebusiness.net/news/commission-launch-era-hubs-boost-regional-innovation>

³⁶ "The Commission will: ... Develop and test a networking framework in support of Europe's R&I ecosystems, building on existing capacities, in order to strengthen excellence and maximise the value of knowledge creation, circulation and use by 2022. " COMM(2020) 628

In addition, initiatives have been announced to 'establish a **new governance structure for Technology Infrastructures**'³⁷, as well as 'strategic support to regions and cities'³⁸ and to 'support Member States to better integrate researchers in smart specialisation strategies in cooperation with industry'.³⁹ These ideas are closely related to the objectives of DIHs and it will be important that these plans are connected to and further enhance already existing mechanisms such as the DIHs.

This new ERA can lay the foundation for a real 'European Research and Innovation Area' that integrates all instruments for transformative policies, not only those of the research domain. In particular the 'governance of technology infrastructures' can benefit from the input of the **DIH network as a stepping stone for the integrated European innovation infrastructure of the twin transition**. These technology infrastructures connect the domains of research, innovation, and industry with the wider systemic transformation dynamics at European scale. Many research and innovation services use the same facilities in competence centres as the diffusion services (testing and piloting). It is therefore very likely that these ERA hubs will share a lot of objectives with (E)DIHs and other EU-level initiatives for research, innovation, education and training to support ecosystems. A joint narrative has to avoid unnecessary duplication and fragmentation, in order to ensure high-quality infrastructure and services.⁴⁰

The new governance for this European Research and Innovation Area represents a window of opportunity that should not be missed for streamlining the instruments for needed massive co-investment.⁴¹ A new ERA can benefit from the input of the DIH network as a stepping stone for the new European innovation infrastructure supporting the twin transition.

6. Conclusions and suggested next steps

The coming Digital Europe Programme, the new Industrial Strategy and other policy initiatives such as the Communication on Europe's digital decade: 2030 digital targets, will provide a stimulating policy environment for advancing more quickly in setting up the European innovation support infrastructure (with focus on test and experimentation facilities in particular) that should become the **backbone** of European transformation policies. The European Research Area can be extended to a common area for support to innovation and technology diffusion across regional eco-systems. The new industrial policy is leveraging the Single Market (thanks to new regulation and standards) as a common transformation space for exploring and upscaling new value propositions in targeted industrial eco-systems (with industrial Alliances).

³⁷ "The Commission will : Support ESFRI to work towards a world-class research infrastructures ecosystem focusing on the broader range of the EU's policy priorities and improve its governance to address the broadened focus of its activity by the end of 2021, and establish a new governance structure for Technology Infrastructures. COMM(2020) 628

³⁸ "Strategic and coordinated support will also be offered to regions and cities building on successful initiatives such as the *Knowledge Exchange Platform*³⁸ (together with the Committee of the Regions) and the Science meets Regions initiative. These will be upgraded to a strategic level ensuring an effective dialogue for setting priorities and promoting synergies between R&I instruments and education and training with adequate mobilisation of cohesion policy funds." COMM(2020) 628

³⁹ The Commission proposes to: ... Institute a dedicated work stream in the ERA Forum for Transition (i) to promote and monitor access to excellence of researchers and institutions from Widening Countries, with Cohesion Policy support, (ii) to support Member States to better integrate researchers in smart specialisation strategies in cooperation with industry, and (iii) help them design measures to support researchers in Widening Countries to improve their skills for excellence in the labour market. This should support low R&I performing countries to increase the excellence of their R&I systems. Member States lagging behind the EU average on highly cited publications should reduce the gap to the EU average by at least one third in the next 5 years. COMM(2020) 628

⁴⁰ 'Smart specialisation' was developed in DG RTD as a response to fragmentation and duplication in the field of public R&I investments for national innovation strategies (see for example [Innovation Union Flagship](#), pp.4), but later shifted to cohesion policy only. "Member States willing to increase the performance of their R&I system towards excellence should be encouraged and supported, building on dedicated Horizon Europe measures and complementarities with smart specialisation strategies under Cohesion Policy." COMM(2020) 628

⁴¹ See Foss policy paper 'The ERA and Smart Specialisation' (<https://friendsofsmartspecialisation.eu/>)

With the **Thought Leadership approach** presented in this paper the FoSS and DIHNet aim to make a contribution to the broader policy development discussion by capitalising on the experience and expectations of the DIH Community regarding internationalisation and collaboration.

Therefore, this paper can be a reference for further development and **work**, on different aspects of the vision for collaborative specialisation in a trans-European support network – e.g. in the context of the EDIHs and the future Digital Transformation Accelerator (DTA). This exploratory work can in particular focus on the implementation of the ‘mapping and matching’ methodology for collaborative specialisation, on analysing preconditions for more corridors of structural collaboration, and on the need of a joint narrative for the European Innovation Support Infrastructure.

The **trailblazer role** of EDIH for the European support infrastructure can be further designed with this ‘thought leadership’ approach. First by using the **Catalogue** of (E)DIH as a stepping stone for an interoperable mapping and matching of services in DIHs to support innovation diffusion, testing and experimentation for joint challenges. In parallel starting the stepwise reinforcement of **corridors** in the EDIH network, to demonstrate this trailblazer capacity for specific challenges. The articulation of corridors **in the 14 European industrial ecosystems** is a strategic way to couple collaborative specialisation in providing services to companies by EDIHs with the European Alliances in selected European strategic value chains.